

Field control of rice caseworm with foliar insecticides

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The rice caseworm *Nymphula depunctalis* is a significant pest of flooded rice in Asia, Africa, and South America, but little published information on its control with insecticides exists. In a trial at IRRI, 11 insecticides were tested as foliar spray (0.75 kg a.i./ ha) 14 days after transplanting (DT) IR40 rice to plots (2 m²) that had been hand-infested with greenhouse-reared 2d- instar larvae (4 larvae/ hill) on the previous day. Each plot was surrounded with levees and plastic sheeting to prevent interplot larval movement.

Caseworm larvae are aquatic; they possess tracheal gills, and live within rice leaves folded into cases secured with silk. During the day, they float on water; at night, they climb plants to cut off leaves to make new cases or feed on severed leaves on the water surface. Cut leaves are symptomatic of caseworm feeding. As the larvae mature they skeletonize the leaf tissue of standing plants, causing the damaged leaves to turn white.

Damage to plants was scored as percentage of tillers with cut leaves and percentage of leaf tissue removed (scraped).

Within the plots, additional information was taken to compare the effect of spraying plants or paddy water separately. In the former, a hill of rice was removed from each plot immediately after spraying and moved to the greenhouse in a plot submerged in insecticide-free water. In the latter, a hill of rice was removed from each plot immediately after spraying and replaced with an insecticide-free potted hill of rice of the same age from the greenhouse. A mylar plastic tube cage was placed over the potted plants and pushed into the soil. A third hill of rice, which represented sprayed plants and paddy water, was likewise caged in each plot after spraying. Ten second-instar larvae were introduced into each cage and mortality was determined 48 hours later by opening the larval cases. The results showed that caseworm larvae were controlled readily with insecticides applied at 0.75 kg a.i./ha (see table). All chemicals tested significantly reduced plant damage and caused high larval mortality compared with the untreated check. MIPC and triazophos were the most toxic and MTMC the least toxic of the chemicals tested. Most insecticides were highly effective when applied to either plants or paddy water. However, when only plants were sprayed, MTMC and endosulfan killed significantly fewer larvae than most of the other insecticides. When only the paddy water was sprayed, MTMC appeared to be the least effective. The results indicate that the rice caseworm can be controlled effectively with one insecticide application after transplanting because this insect is a pest only during the tillering stage. Future trials should test insecticides at lower dosages.